

Externally Activated Self-Healing in Structural Composites via Embedded Conductive Networks

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Outline

- Background and Motivation
- Self-Healing in Synthetic Materials
- Thermal Remending Technique and Wireless Induction Heating Concept
- Composite Construction and Thermal Characterization
- Comparative Self-Healing Performance Study
- Summary and Future Work

Fiber-Reinforced Polymer (FRP) Composites and SWaP+C

- **Fiber-reinforced composites possess:**
High specific stiffness (1 – 3x) that of metals and strength (5 – 8x), enabling significant weight savings (20 – 50%), good corrosion resistance, and customization of geometry and materials.

Automotive

Aerospace

Naval

Wind Energy

- **Size, Weight, and Power + Cost (SWaP+C) framework:**
Aims to maintain or enhance mechanical performance while decreasing fuel consumption and emissions.

- The Boeing 787 Dreamliner is made from 50% composite material vs. only 6% for the 747.

DAAAM 28 (2017)

- Wind turbine blades are comprised of 90% composite material.

Damage in Laminated Fiber Composites

- Hierarchical materials with structural advantage, but also inherent susceptibility to multi-scale damage – particularly delamination.
- Delamination detection is difficult and manual repairs are costly.

Pristine Laminate

Interlaminar Delamination

Repairs costly/time consuming

www.dsto.defence.gov.au

Propensity for catastrophic failure

USAF Hilltop Times

Self-healing Strategies

- Next-generation composites are envisioned to self-heal damage like biological materials.

Biological Self-Healing

Soft Materials (e.g., Skin Lesion)

Biomimetics 2 (2017)

Structural Materials (e.g., Broken Bone)

Adv. Mater. 22 (2010)

Synthetic Self-Healing Strategies

Capsule-based

Nature 409 (2001)

Limitations:

- Single-heal
- Small-scale repair

Vascular

Adv. Mater. 22 (2010)

- Mixing difficult
- Blockages
- Scarring

Intrinsic

Dynamic rebonding

Damage restoration

Nature 540 (2016)

Advantages:

- Multiple-heals
- No external agent

Soft Materials

Angew. Chem. 51 (2012)

- Interface contact
- Room-temperature repair

Structural Materials

Science 295 (2002)

- Elevated temperature repair

Extrinsic-Intrinsic
Thermal Remending

In situ Thermal Remending Technique (Resistive Heating)

- Intrinsic healing of poly(ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) enables **unprecedented repeatability** for *in situ* self-healing.

3D-printing onto preform substrate

Pristine multifunctional composite laminate

Internal delamination damage

Self-healing via *in situ* thermal remending

U.S. Patent No. 16/944,675 Compos. Part A 185 (2024)

Compos. Sci. Technol. 240 (2023)

Textile Resistive Heaters

Copper Bus Bar

E-glass Shroud

Resistive Heater Specimen

- Foreign components (resistive heaters, busbars, and wiring)
- Complex composite manufacturing procedure

Research Question:

Can we achieve the same level of self-healing without wired connections?

Wireless Thermal Remending Platform (Induction Heating)

Induction Heating – An Introduction

- Induction heating enables **rapid, non-contact, localized heating** of ferromagnetic and **electrically conductive materials**.

Induction Coil Schematic

Comsol.com

Induction Coil Cross Section

Comsol.com

Governing Equations

$$p = \rho |\mathbf{J}|^2$$

- p : power density
- ρ : materials resistivity
- $|\mathbf{J}|$: current density magnitude

Low frequency Induction Heating

Comsol.com

Magnetic Hysteresis Losses

Magnetism and Magnetic Material 1 (2024)

Global Eddy Current Pattern

Edge Effects from Sample Boundary

Resulting Temperature Profile

(i)

Compos Part A 37 (2006)

Resulting Temperature Profile

(ii)

(iii)

High frequency Induction Heating (Skin Effect)

Comsol.com

In Situ Thermal Remending with Inductive Heater Strategy

Goal: simplify composite construction by leveraging metallic interlayers for non-contact heating.

Virgin EMAA Pellets

In-house Filament

3D Printing EMAA

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM)

FDM Process

Print head registration with textile substrate

Glass Composite Cross Section

X-ray Computed Tomography Reconstruction

EMAA patterned woven fiber

GFRP (Glass) layup (16 plies):
[90/0]₂/90/H/0/90/0/EMAA/90/0/90/H/[90/0]₂
CFRP (Carbon) layup (6 plies):
0/90/H/0/EMAA/90/H/0/90
Post-cure: 2h @ 121°C + 2h @ 150°C

Carbon Composite Cross Section

Electrically Conductive Mesh Interlayer (i.e., Susceptor)

Induction Heating Thermal Characterization

- Evaluated several copper and aluminum meshes varying in weight from 0.015 – 0.086 psf with a detailed study of the lighter meshes.
- Thermal gradient profiles between meshes are comparable.
- Energy consumption during induction heating ranges from 4.61 kJ to 12.25 kJ, costs at this scale are negligible.
- Down selection based on weight, favoring Cu over AL for material compatibility.

Electrically Conductive Mesh Susceptors

Cu-015

Cu-029

Al-015

Al-028

Strength, Weight, and Power + Cost (SWaP+C) Comparison

Induction Heating Test Setup

Double Cantilever Beam* (DCB) schematic

Rapid heating of Inductive method Temporal Plot

Governing Equations

$$\dagger G_I = \frac{1}{b} \frac{\Delta U}{\Delta a}$$

$$\Delta U = \int_0^{\hat{\delta}} P d\hat{\delta} \Big|_{\Delta a}$$

$$\ddagger \hat{\eta} := \frac{G_{IC}^{healed}}{G_{IC}^{virgin}} \times 100$$

*ASTM D-5528

†J. Mater. Sci. Lett. 8 (1989)

‡Adv. Mater. 26 (2014)

Self-healing Performance Comparison

Glass Inductive

Carbon Inductive

Summary and Future Work

- We improve *in situ* thermal remending by **eliminating wired connections and extraneous components**, enabling **targeted, scalable, and energy-efficient non-contact heating** for self-healing.
- Identified a **cumulative time-at-temperature** correlation where extended dwell periods achieve **equivalent glass healing** and **improved carbon healing efficiency (85% vs. 50%)** compared to resistive methods.
- Future work will explore **system optimization** for transfer to real-world applications.

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Questions

International Conference of Self-healing Materials (ICSHM2026)

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials
July 8-10
Drexel University, Philadelphia, USA

Event highlights:

- Connect with experts and peers from around the world
- Discover emerging technologies, methods, and applications
- Present your latest research and gain valuable feedback
- Explore historic city - Philadelphia, PA birthplace of the United States

 July 8-10, 2026

 Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, USA

 <https://icshm2026.org>

Abstract Submission Open: Now
Abstract Submission Close: 15 February 2026

JULY 8-10

ICSHM

10th International Conference on Self-healing Materials

Conference Chairs

Prof. Jason Patrick
(NC State University)

Prof. Amir Farnham
(Drexel University)

Backup Slides

Control Experiments

Rapid Inductive vs. Resistive Thermal Characterization

Rapid/Dwell Thermal Characterization

EMAA Evolution with Heal Cycle

